

Validation Requirements

Table 1: Ethical AI requirements used in the experiment.

ID	Requirement	Principle
R1	User consent must always be explicitly obtained.	Non-maleficence
R2	Clear documentation describing how and from which sources the training and testing data were collected must be available.	Transparency
R3	Personal or sensitive information contained in training data must not be exposed.	Privacy
R4	Unnecessary computational resource usage and energy consumption during system operation should be minimized.	Sustainability
R5	Human review and intervention must be possible when automated decisions significantly impact users.	Human Oversight
R6	Discriminatory outcomes across protected demographic groups should be minimized when generating predictions or recommendations.	Fairness